

INTERPRETATION OF SOME INFORMATION FROM THE WORK “HISTORY OF ANCIENT TASHKANT”

Dordona MASHRBALIYEVA,

Namdu, History student

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Abstract: This article provides information about the unique representative of the Kokan school of historiography, Muhammad Salih Tashkandiy, and his work "History of Tashkent" and the history of the city of Tashkent in the 19th century, its inhabitants, gates, walls, and governors of Tashkent, and their political activities.

Keywords: Muhammad Salih Tashkandi, "History of Tashkent", Tashkent, Russian Empire, Kokhan Khanate, Tashkent gates, strategic and economic center, Yunus Khan, Lashkar beglar, Normuhammed Qushbegi.

ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ НЕКОТОРЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИИ ИЗ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА “ИСТОРИЯ ДРЕВНЕГО ТАШКАНТА”

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены сведения об уникальном представителе Коканской школы историографии Мухаммаде Салихе Ташкандий и его труде «История Ташкента» и истории города Ташкента XIX века, его жителей, ворот, стен, и губернаторы Ташкента и их политическая деятельность.

Ключевые слова: Мухаммад Салих Ташканди, «История Ташкента», Ташкент, Российская империя, Коканское ханство, Ташкентские ворота, стратегический и экономический центр, Юнус-хан, Лашкар беглар, Нормухаммед Кушбеги.

INTRODUCTION

Science is a force that elevates a person to heights. Science is one of the factors that determines the further development of not only a person, but also the entire nation. A developing and successful nation will never be dependent, it will never lose its freedom. If we look at history, the countries that have reached a high level of development (Great Britain, France, Germany, Japan, the United States, the Russian Empire) compared to their less developed countries (India, African countries, Latin America, Southeast Asian countries, Central Asia) began to turn them into a dependent state, because of which the states are not aware of the outside world, their borders are close, and they consider any scientific progress as superstition, so they began to lag behind other states. Through these examples, we can see how important scientific, cultural and scientific relations are. In particular, during the 16th - 19th centuries, our motherland Central Asia became the focus of attention of the Russian Empire and Great Britain, which developed from us due to its isolation from the outside world, slow scientific development, lack of military development, and strong enmity in the khanates. As a result, the Russian Empire began to take advantage of the internal conflicts and disagreements between the Central Asian khanates and its military backwardness. However, literature, history, calligraphy, music, religion did not stop developing during this period. We can learn about the socio-economic and cultural life during the military operations of the Russian Empire in our country from the written sources of that time. One of such historians is Muhammad Salih Tashkandi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Muhammad Salihkhoja Tashkandi was born around 1230-1231 in the Koryogdi neighborhood of Tashkent in a family belonging to the famous Sheikh Umar Bogistani. His grandfather Mullah Muhammad Rahimkhoja was one of the educated people. He received his

primary education from his grandfather, Mulla Abdurahimkhoja (he was the imam of the Bekmuhammadbi mosque located in Qiyat neighborhood) [1. - B. 245.] received. In 1840-1849, Muhammad Salihkhoja was educated at Eshankulidohhoh, Lashkar Beklarbegi, and Khoja Ahror madrasas in Tashkent. From the 50s of the 19th century, Muhammad Salihkhoja diligently began to improve his knowledge. In particular, in 1853-1854, he traveled to Namangan and studied with a scientist named Eshon Bagakhjoja. In 1856, he went to Bukhara and met famous scientists and scholars in this city until 1862. Since 1863, he has served as an imam in the mosque where his grandfather was an imam, and at the same time he is also teaching [2. - B. 245.].

"History of Tashkent" written by Muhammad Salihkhoja in 1863-1888 is the only book dedicated to the history of Tashkent. This work contains valuable information about the political, socio-economic, and cultural life of the Kokan Khanate, in particular, Tashkent, in the second half of the 19th century. The scientific nature of the work is that the historical and geographical information about the city of Tashkent and the region is given in detail and consistently, and the image of Tashkent in the 19th century is perfectly written through this work [3. - B. 149.]. For example: Tashkent is shown as an administrative unit with the name of the city. He points out that a number of cities, villages and regions are included in the region. In the work, its territory is indicated approximately from the beginning to the end of the Sayhun (Syr Darya) river. In another place, the author defines the eastern border of Tashkent with the Kurama mountains and states that Tashkent's property includes the lands from Syrdarya to the land of Christians, to China and Gulja belonging to China.

The work contains information about the historical and topographical situation of Tashkent. In particular, the following is written in the work about the gates of Tashkent. Noting that there were 12 gates there as early as the 14th century, he connects them with the name of Amir Temur and tries to explain the etymology of the names of the gates. According to the author, when Amir Temur captured Tashkent for the second time, he entrusted its 12 gates to the control of tribal and clan leaders.

The author explains them as follows: Qiyat gate - in the east, on behalf of the Qiyat tribe; Turkish gate - on behalf of the Turkish tribe; Uzbek gate - on behalf of the Uzbek tribe; Takhtapuli gate - named after the city of Mecca, the mother of cities; Karasaroy Gate - in the name of the Karasaroy tribe; He explained that the gates of Sugbaniyan, Kokcha, Kamandaron, Kangli, Beshyogoch, and Qatagan were named after the tribes with these names. The naming of gates with the names of such clans is typical only for the gates of Tashkent, and such a situation is almost never observed in the gates of Bukhara, Samarkand, Kokand. The reason for this is that in the 18th century, tribes moved to the vicinity of Tashkent.

Ko'kan, Khiyabon, (Kamolon) Kirilmos, Beshyogoch and Kokcha gates are mentioned the most in the work during the description of the events of the invasion of the Russian Empire. The foot soldiers of the occupiers entered from Khiyabon and Kirilmos gates, and from Kokcha gate, cavalry entered. Qiyat gate, which is said to belong to the era of Amir Temur, is the name of the gate in later times, and it was also called Parkent in ancient times. The alley gate appears in Russian sources in the form of Kamolon [4. - B. 62.]. After that, the author touched on the work done to strengthen the city and said that the city had a high wall in the XIV-XV centuries and that its wall existed in Tashkent during the reign of Darvish Khan, the son of Barak Khan (XVI), and then Abdullah Khan II (XVI). notes. In later periods, the city wall became a ruin due to the attack

of the external enemy and the influence of time, the author writes that the city was restored during the time of Yunus Khan and his successors (1784-1808).

In 1808, Tashkent was occupied by the troops of Kokhan Khan. By the time of Lashkar Beklarbegi, the viceroy of Tashkent, the wall was again in ruins, says Muhammad Salih. That is why Lashkar Beklarbegi wanted to rebuild the city wall, surrounded the city with a high wall, built towers and gates everywhere [5. - B. 14-15.].

In addition, information about the population of Tashkent is also given in the work. Although the author does not provide specific information about the population of Tashkent city or its regions, it helps to determine the population of Tashkent in the 19th century and its composition. He emphasizes that the appearance of the population is wheat-colored, with beautiful eyebrows, black eyes, tall and medium height, ambitious, ambitious, hospitable, hospitable and intelligent. In the work, he listed the composition of the population of Tashkent, such as toras, akobirs, nobles and ayons, merchants, artisans, raiyats, citizens. Slave labor was also used in Tashkent, and they mention Abyssinian and Chinese slaves who performed military and household tasks. There were also Indian and Iranian slaves. Also, cattle-raising population was mentioned under the name of elatiya and kaboiliya, they are the general name of Kyrgyz and Kazakhs who pay zakat to the Tashkent government [4. - B. 83.]. These clans and clans had a strong role in the political life of Tashkent, including Salimsoqtor from Devonbegi neighborhood - amir ul-umaro, Rustamtora - ataliq, Olimto in the kurlitoy with representatives of 92 clans during the period of "Four governorships". 'ra - propeller driver, Bobokhontora - was appointed army captain. Then they all unanimously elected Yunus Khan as the governor of the region. In 1863-1864, Khan of Koqan, Sultan Saidkhan, also allocated lands around Tashkent for his clan to Siddigtora and his brother Arslontora, who fled from the Russians. For this reason, it is said that Kazakhs or clans such as Sanchigli, Sergeli, Duglut, Argin and Tamgali lived in the east, north and west of Tashkent [4. - B. 84.].

Also, in the work, representatives of the upper class of Tashkent provide information about governors and persons in high management. They are mainly the governors of the period after the conquest of Tashkent by Khan Olim Khan (1798-1810). They are: Salimsoktora Tashkandi, Lashkar beglarbegi, Sultan Muhammad ibn Umarkhan, Muhammad Sharif father, Mallakhan, Salimsokkhan, Mulla Holbek, Aziz parvanachi, Normuhammad Qushbegi, Niyozmuhammad, Tursunmuhammad, Shomonkhoja Qushbegi, Sofibek Davronbek son .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the work, the author spoke a lot about the Lashkar beklarbegi among the governors of Tashkent. He repaired the walls of Tashkent by the order of Kokhan Khan Muhammad Alikhan (Madalikhon), dug a trench around Orda, and took possession of vacant land around the city, built a madrasah, caravanserai, rabot and mills in the city. In 1835, he received the title of "beklarbegi", a title that very few officials in the khanate received. Another Tashkent governor, Qanoat, received the title of "patriarchal ghazi" after a battle against Russian soldiers in Pishpak (Bishkek) during the reign of Koqan Khan Mallakhon. Before becoming the mayor of Tashkent, most of the hokims served as the hokims of surrounding administrative units such as Boka, Kurama, Ovliq, Turkestan, and Shymkent, which was a test for the candidates to manage the largest and most important region in the khanate. Khans appointed their brothers or trusted officials from Kokan to Tashkent only in some critical situations. For example, Mallakhon, Sultan Muradbek, and Yunuskhan Munshi were appointed governors during the period of Kokan Khan Khudoyarkhan and during the Russian occupation. The authority of governors in Tashkent was stronger than the authority of governors

of other regions. The reason is that Tashkent was a rich region located at the crossroads of major trade and industry and caravan routes. The governors were replaced by the khans at any time, depending on the political situation or their performance.

CONCLUSIONS

During the reign of Muslim Khangul Mingbashi and Alimquli Amirakar, who seized the central power, they were in charge of appointing and removing the governors of Tashkent. But some governors, in particular, Lashkar Beklarbegi, Normuhammad Qoshbegi, Qanoat Ataliq, were the most influential among the Tashkent governors, and they were able to influence the political situation in the khanate. In particular, Lashkar Beklarbegi led the Tashkent army during the march of Koqan Khan Muhammad Alikha to Kashgar, and the Koqan army during the march to Oratepa against Amir Nasrullah in 1840. Normuhammad Koshbegi, in 1852, opposed the government of Muslim Thousand, took the protection of those fleeing from his persecution, and led a group against Kipchaks in the whole country. In 1862, Qataghan protested against the government, which raised Shahmurad Khan ibn Salimsakh Khan as khan, and raised Khudoyar Khan, who was in the territory of the emirate, as khan [4. - B. 108–110.]. It can be seen that Tashkent was strategically important due to its location, and the political positions of the governors appointed to it were also high. The government of the Russian Empire paid its first attention to Tashkent because it is located at the intersection of important caravan routes. The city is also fully self-sufficient with water resources and is considered a favorable area for agriculture and animal husbandry.

References:

1. Madraimov A., Fuzailova G. Manbashunoslik. - T.: National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan, 2008.
2. Akhmedov B. Sources of the history of Uzbekistan. - T.: Teacher, 2001.
3. Ergashev B. Source studies and historiography. – Samarkand.: SamDu, 2021.
4. Sultanov O'. A. Muhammad Salihkhoja and his work "History of Tashkent". - T.: Uzbekistan, 2009.
5. Orinboev A., Buriev O. In the description of Tashkent Muhammed Salih. – – T.: Science, 1983.
6. Internet sites: WWW.Ziyonet.uz. SHosh.UZ, WWW- now.org.